
Leo Strauss on Returning: Some Methodological Aspects

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Abstract: Leo Strauss (1899-1973) was but one out of a number of German-Jewish thinkers emerging around 1930 who sought to return to the ancients, but no one expressed this idea more radically and with greater vigor. This paper examines Strauss's project of returning as it was formed around 1930 and subsequently clarified and expanded. The focus on "methodological" aspects indicates that the concern is not only with the question of *why* such a return seemed necessary for Strauss, but also *how* he sought to do it. After providing an outline of his principal considerations and their respective theoretical contexts, then, the article also seeks to examine the philosophical thinking and writing in action. The body of writings to be examined include two lecture manuscripts of 1930 and 1931, with a brief view towards Strauss's early master work *Philosophy and Law* (1935) and his lecture "Jerusalem and Athens" (1967).

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1. Introduction: Strauss and the German-Jewish Return to the Ancients

Leo Strauss was but one out of several German-Jewish thinkers around 1930 who fancied a return to the ancients, but no one expressed this idea more radically and with greater vigor than Strauss. Strauss has been compared with Karl Löwith in this respect, but the two knew well about the fundamental difference. Strauss did not merely propose to revisit or re-read the tradition of Platonic philosophy but to return to Platonic philosophizing altogether. From around 1930 onwards he worked out a philosophical and scholarly project showing that it is actually possible to return; or at least that the reasons that seemed to speak against the possibility of returning were based on unwarranted assumptions. As he wrote to Löwith in 1933: "The abstract historicist objections are known to me – but I believe that in the end they present themselves differently than at the beginning. To cut a long story short: I must see whether I 'get through' (*ob ich 'durchkomme'*)."¹

One reason why Strauss stands out here is that he coupled the underlying distinction between ancients and moderns with the renewal of the quarrel between Jerusalem and Athens. The return to the ancients therefore comes with a simultaneous return to the quarrel between

reason and revelation as the principal topic of philosophy.² Another, more obvious reason is his anti-historicism. Rather than as a historical reminiscence, returning to antiquity was conceptualized as an actual possibility, or as Strauss explained to Löwith, "an *eternal* possibility."³ But it also seemed as a necessity, as the only viable alternative to the unviable modern political ideas: "I *really* believe – although that apparently seems fanciful to you – that the perfect political order as sketched by Plato and Aristotle *is* the perfect political order. Or do you believe in the world state?"⁴

Löwith, too, sought to return to antiquity. He imagined this return as a cosmic "eternal recurrence" that was in principal agreement with his taste for the 19th century (Kierkegaard, Burckhardt, Nietzsche, and others). In other words, he was much more than Strauss in principal agreement with modernity. But undoubtedly they had something in common. To generalize the matter a bit with regard to the circle of Strauss, Löwith, Klein, Jonas, Arendt, Krüger and Gadamer: to a different degree they were all Nietzscheans and Heideggerians around 1930. The will to return to the ancients had been fueled by Nietzsche and Heidegger, and the return was to be carried out on the philosophical basis of Nietzsche and Heidegger. To give a quote from Strauss's "Unspoken Prologue" to Jacob Klein: "Heidegger had opened [a possibility] without intending it: the possibility of a genuine return to classical philosophy, to the philosophy of Aristotle and Plato, a return with open eyes and in full clarity about the infinite difficulties it entails."⁵ Later they all wrestled with the problem of philosophy and politics as posed by Heidegger's affiliation with National Socialism; but that problem had not yet begun to play out in the formation of their philosophical projects.

The option for Heidegger entailed a turn against neo-Kantianism. The quarrels during the Weimar Republic between neo-Kantians and their increasingly radical opponents are legendary. One focal point of the turn against neo-Kantianism in the 1920s was the opposition against the neo-Kantian interpretation of Plato and Aristotle. The event that triggered this opposition was Heidegger's early Aristotle lecture, by which he established his reputation as an excellent interpreter of classical philosophical texts.⁶ This intensive interpretation came to be seen as the opposite to the neo-Kantian reading of Plato as a proto-Kantian that was codified in Paul Natorp's *Platos Ideenlehre* (1903).

The entire polemics against the waning neo-Kantianism in the 1920s came with a radical break from

the philosophy of culture. There are quite some inner-philosophical reasons for the discontent with philosophy of culture, but the German-Jewish philosophers around 1930 had good reason to register the changes in the understanding of culture very sharply. That reason was the looming failure of German-Jewish assimilation, with its promise of *Bildung* and *Kultur*. The crisis of culture was accompanied by a double reawakening of religion (Rosenzweig and the return to Judaism) and the political (the exposure to anti-Semitism and the increasing plausibility of the Zionist option). German-Jewish philosophy around 1930 was largely situated in the force-field of culture, religion and the political. Strauss came closer than any other of these philosophers to a theoretical outline of this force-field. He is the principal critic of “culture” here, and his methodology of returning is first and foremost designed as a departure from the latent culturalism of his contemporaries.

2. Progress or Return?

The shifts in the understanding of culture also came with ever-increasing doubts in the idea of progress, both in the sense of the perfectibility of man and of social progress toward a world society in which, among other aspects, the Jews would no longer be discriminated against. Strauss spelled out the consequence most clearly: The limits of progress allowed for the first time to consider the possibility of returning.

Strauss’s notion of “returning” had a much wider spectrum than the return to the ancients. That was best explained in his 1952 lecture “Progress or Return?,” which was meant to explain the “contemporary crisis of Western civilization” to a Jewish audience and with regard to the problem of Jewish modernity. The text starts with the marvelous statement “that progress has become a problem – that it could seem as if progress has led us to the brink of an abyss, and it is therefore necessary to consider alternatives to it.”⁷ Spoken seven years after the end of WWII, these words are little spectacular with regard to the diagnosis. Progress *had* become a problem even for the most hard-boiled progressivists. The surprise is in the suggestion that it might therefore be useful to “consider alternatives” to progress: Whereas many of his colleagues sought to convince their audiences that the abyss of progress demanded an unabated and often radicalized commitment to the principles of a *true* progress (which had unfortunately not yet begun), Strauss suggested that it might be better “to stop where we are, or else, if this should be impossible, to return.”⁸

Strauss emphasized the religious meaning of the term, its origin in the Hebrew notion of *teshuva*. This notion of *teshuva* is still employed today when formerly orthodox people who had abandoned Judaism return or seek to return to the Jewish creed, with all the psychological and social hardships that come with it. Strauss emphasized this meaning of returning as repentance; or the acknowledgment that one had once been on the right way and then turned to the wrong way. In other words, he discussed the fate of Western civilization within a framework borrowed from orthodox Judaism, to which he himself did not belong. In that framework the progress that had led to the

brink of an abyss came to be seen as abandonment; and abandonment in the sense of deviation or sin had again to be abandoned to allow for redemption and restoration. This appropriation of that orthodox narrative was both playful and serious. It was playful in the sense that some random elements of orthodoxy had become disposable for a non-orthodox philosophical purpose, almost as in post-modernism. It was serious in the sense that it outlined a way to disentangle oneself from the modern assumptions of history and progress. The position of orthodoxy provided a critical standpoint from which modernity, and in particular modern philosophy with its proclivity toward irrationalism, could be judged of.⁹

To make sense out of Strauss’s notion of “return,” then, I suggest that the contrast between modernity and antiquity creates a tension within the modern world, and that this contrast is primarily a *critical* difference introduced by Strauss into 20th-century philosophy. Whereas for some of his contemporaries, modernity was to be judged by its socio-economic flipside, for Strauss modernity was to be tried in a “pre-modern court.”¹⁰ It was this idea that made Straussian political philosophy the principal alternative to the latent progressivism of 20th-century thought. Strauss was immensely concerned with the question of why it is necessary and how it is possible to return, and perhaps this is what he will stand for once he will be more properly situated in the overall history of 20th-century philosophy. The idea of return is a challenge here, because it is easily exposed to the objection of historicism: One cannot turn back the wheel of history, or go back in time. And indeed, how could a return-to-whatever seem to be a viable solution? But if the suggestion is right that the primary purpose of returning was to gain an outside perspective on the present, then Strauss’s project of returning is actually rather simple and entirely realistic. It was merely too far away from the consensus to be easily digestible for his colleagues. He needed to start from the ground up to explain it to them.

His writings from 1930 onward contain numerous methodological reflections and textual strategies pertaining to the proper way of returning. These reflections involve criticism against scientific methodologies, but they also carefully outline and exemplify a methodology of political philosophizing. The crucial aspect of returning was the *transition* from the modern assumptions to the respective subject matter as it was originally understood. Strauss was aware that the political understanding he sought to arrive at was not evident from the beginning, so he needed to *lead* from the seemingly evident premises to the premises of political thinking. For this reason he was immensely occupied with the starting point, the proper way to begin. Methodological reflections are chiefly concerned with this starting point. Therefore one must read the beginnings of Strauss’s texts with disproportionate care.

3. A Double Return: Leo Strauss around 1930

By Strauss’s own testimony, his early book on Spinoza (completed in 1928, published 1930) “was based on the premise, sanctioned by powerful prejudice, that a return to pre-modern philosophy is impossible.” As he de-

clared, the ensuing “change of orientation” had “found its first expression, not entirely by accident,” in his review article on Carl Schmitt’s *The Concept of the Political* (1932).¹¹ The much-quoted statement has often been understood to mean that the “change of orientation” was due to the encounter with Carl Schmitt; this encounter has henceforth been cast as the foundational event of Strauss’s political philosophizing. Given these far-reaching conclusions drawn from a late recollection, then, it is extremely important to locate the “change of orientation” more precisely in his writings around 1930. The “Notes on Carl Schmitt” was the first *published* article that expressed the idea of returning, but that idea had floated around in several earlier lecture manuscripts and drafts. These texts, which in the meantime have been published in English, provide a micrological view into the genesis of the idea and its initial contexts.

The first outline of the idea of returning is to be found in the text “Religious Situation of the Present,” a lecture manuscript for a camp of the Zionist student group Kadi-mah in December 1930. Here Strauss presented the idea of returning as an alternative to Karl Mannheim’s sociology of knowledge, on whom he had also penned a masterful polemical essay a year earlier.¹² This starting point was “not entirely by accident,” too.¹³ It was the highly advanced and entirely formalistic methodology of modern social science provided by Mannheim that led Strauss to describe the necessity to stop and return: Strauss outlined the return to premodern philosophizing as a principal alternative to the sociology of knowledge.

The choice of Mannheim as a scapegoat was not entirely arbitrary. He is no longer well known today, but after his master work *Ideology and Utopia* (1929) he was supposed to be the next big thing in academic and wider public discussions.¹⁴ The book was reviewed by Hannah Arendt, Max Horkheimer, Paul Tillich and Herbert Marcuse and others. As Strauss quipped, Mannheim belonged to the “most progressive” and “most expert” part of the German-Jewish intelligentsia.¹⁵ It was a matter of up-to-dateness to take on his master book, but Strauss also needed to defend his own work against its pretension: If the sociology of knowledge were able to provide a consistent answer to “the question,” as Strauss rephrased the concern with the situation of the present, then his own scholarly project would be entirely useless.

His conclusion was that Mannheim’s teaching is “sophistic,” and this claim was itself a blend of modern and premodern perspectives. First, it was built upon the Socratic premise of a categorical difference between sophists and philosophers. Second, this difference was not limited to the temporal and spatial setting of Greek philosophy. Just like the “real philosophy” of antiquity, so its counterpart of sophistry was an “eternal possibility.”¹⁶ The larger article on Mannheim that never came to life was to be named “Sophistry of our time.”¹⁷ Strauss also continued his studies on Florian Znaniecki in the early 1940s under the same working title, but he never published these studies either.¹⁸ He sometimes suggested that modern philosophy and social science as such were sophistic, but the sociology of knowledge was the principal and most elaborated spokesman for modern sophistry. The sociology of knowledge embodied the modern know-it-all scholarly habit, whereas “real philosophy” was

based on knowing to know nothing. As such, the sociology of knowledge was a serious competitor for Strauss, although this concern did not translate much into his publication record. The principal commentary on the matter is his ironic appropriation of the term “sociology of knowledge” at the beginning of *Persecution and the Art of Writing* (1952). One could be tempted to understand this commentary as an example of Strauss’s mastery of esoteric writing – but he did everything completely in the open, and not “between the lines” (as the famous metaphorical expression of esoteric writing goes).

Strauss criticized the sociology of knowledge for its failure to account for the difference between “everything that pretends to be knowledge” and “genuine knowledge,” and between intellectuals and philosophers.¹⁹ The strategic link here is between “intellectuals” and sophists. The sophist as understood by Strauss (following Plato) “contents himself with appearances with regard to being and to the true,”²⁰ and that seemed to count for the sociologist of knowledge more than for any other current teaching. Strauss presented his own “sociology of philosophy” ironically as a “province” or “subdivision” of the sociology of knowledge; but actually he sought to outline the fundamental difference between the two: “Sociology of knowledge emerged in a society which took for granted the essential harmony between thought and society or between intellectual progress and social progress. It was more concerned with the relation of the different types of thought to different types of society than with the fundamental relation of thought as such to society as such.”²¹ As Strauss added, sociology of knowledge regarded the different philosophies as “exponents of different societies or classes or ethnic spirits.” It thereby disregarded the tension between philosophy and society, or as Strauss put it: “the possibility that all philosophers form a class by themselves.” Strauss further explained that this failure was due to the fact that the sociology of knowledge knew only of 19th and 20th-century Western thought. The tension between philosophy and society could only be understood by turning “to other ages” and “other climates.”²² His own sociology of philosophy was built upon the medieval Islamic and Jewish Enlightenment; and there he famously found “a peculiar type of literature, in which the truth about all things is presented exclusively between the lines.”²³

To return to Strauss’s early criticism of the sociology of knowledge: “Conspicuousness,” as he called the attitude of Mannheim and others, was the epitome of a pseudo-comprehensive view, based on the methodological abstractions of sociological value relativism. It sought to arrive at a scientific understanding of the current situation through a synthesis, or a synopsis, of the present-day viewpoints. The task of the sociologist of knowledge was to synthesize the plurality of ideologies and standpoints into a unified theory of the present. This solution was open to the objection that not all of these views were worthy of being synthesized, or that all these views might be fundamentally wrong. As Strauss declared: “Can the possibility ruled out from the start that all these interpretations may be blind to the same fundamental facts; that one thus never even encounters these fundamental facts if one orients oneself from the beginning only by these viewpoints?”²⁴

The argument against Mannheim's social science teaching can be summarized as follows. First he argued, to come to know the present just as it *is* one must become free of the present, and this freedom must be won. Second he argued that it was not so clear whether the task of understanding really was to know "the situation of the present"; for mankind has always had a present, but why need one be concerned with it in the first place? Third, Strauss explained the difficulties of understanding by way of the Platonic allegory of the cave. He referred to this allegory as a description of the *natural* difficulties of philosophizing, adding that the problem of a plurality of opinions was merely a by-product of these natural difficulties. Fourth, Strauss added a non-natural difficulty of philosophizing, referring to Maimonides's discussion in the *More Nevuchim* of Alexander of Aphrodisias. According to Maimonides, Alexander of Aphrodisias added a fourth reason to the three natural difficulties of philosophizing, and that is the "habituation to writings in which they [the multitude] firmly believe and to which they are habituated." In Strauss's words, the fourth reason is given "by the fact that a tradition resting on revelation has entered the world of philosophy," and hence "the freedom of philosophizing is fundamentally limited."²⁵

The argument certainly became more powerful in later versions. But it seems worthwhile to follow the movement indicated by these four steps: from the obsession with the present situation to a step back from the present situation, to the natural situation of philosophizing, and at last to the unnatural difficulty of philosophizing added by the fact of revelation. Strauss had thereby *led* the reader from the sociological preoccupation with the present situation into the fundamental tension between reason and revelation as the principal problem of philosophical thought. This movement from the most obvious things to the most important things forms a recurring pattern in Strauss's methodology of returning to the ancients. It was also a return from the unnatural difficulties of philosophizing to the natural difficulties, as depicted in the allegory of the *second* cave, from which one must free oneself in order to climb back at least to the Platonic cave.²⁶ No matter whether Schmitt or Mannheim (or Ebbinghaus) was the first target of Strauss's criticism, and no matter whether this criticism came as a polite scholarly argument or a polemical attack – the starting point for Strauss's notion of returning to the ancients is to be found in the antinomies of the moderns, and in particular of his contemporaries. In his polemical interventions he was immensely concerned with the possibility of finding a viewpoint that would not merely add to the "anarchy of opinions" (Mannheim) or the irreducible plurality of viewpoints. According to Mannheim, this plurality was to be reached by way of a synthesis. According to Carl Schmitt, it was to be shattered by the force of a sudden, arbitrary decision between friend and enemy.

It was the quest for a viewpoint beyond the plurality of current viewpoints that made the appeal to the ancients necessary for Strauss. He had been searching for a comprehensive viewpoint from early on. His early writings in the context of German Zionism feature a heterogeneous field of positions and critical strategies, but they lack a clear focus that would have organized these positions into a coherent view. He saw the "intellectual situation" as a

battlefield of culture, religion and the political, but his own positions – particularly in the quarrels between orthodoxy and political Zionism – were almost interchangeable. The only stable element was the recurring polemics against the notion of "culture." The return to premodern philosophizing provided this critical work in the forcefield of culture, religion and the political with a clear focus and purpose.

The first to note the similarity of Strauss's "method of critical argumentation" in the two essays on Mannheim and Schmitt was Karl Löwith. He conceded that the reasoning was impressive, but he sought to evade the consequence that the criticism applied to his own philosophical endeavor, too. As Löwith argued, even if he was indeed caught up by historical relativism, he could not overcome it by *not* starting from the (necessarily polemical) situation of the present.²⁷ But Strauss, too, started from the situation of the present. The question was how to proceed from there, and how to become free from the starting point. Löwith noticed that Strauss argued from a different position. An expression in Strauss's texts of the early 1930s captures this difference well: It was all about a "horizon." In the Mannheim critique the task was to gain "the horizon" in which radical questions and answers are alone possible. In his *Comments* on Carl Schmitt he announced right at the beginning the need for "a horizon beyond liberalism." As he explained: "[Schmitt's] critique of liberalism occurs in the horizon of liberalism; his unilateral tendency is restrained by the still unvanquished 'systematics of liberal thought.'"²⁸

4. Returning to Maimonides

Strauss subsequently gained a better understanding of this new horizon through his main scholarly project at the time, a new interpretation of the Islamic and Jewish Enlightenment of the Middle Ages, which found its first literary expression in 1931 and eventually morphed into the early master work *Philosophy and Law* (1935). He presented some of his findings in his Berlin lecture of 1931, "Cohen and Maimonides." A brief look at the introduction is helpful.

Strauss's copious explanation of the "and" in the title demonstrates the reorientation in the most literal sense: It entailed a change of perspective. As he explained, the "and" between Cohen and Maimonides "gives the impression that we, as if sovereign spectators or even judges, wanted to allow both these outstanding men to *pass before* us."²⁹ This procedure would be appropriate, not only for the sociologist of knowledge, but basically for all "theory"-led approaches that are certain of their own epistemic superiority. Strauss started from the premise that Maimonides was inaccessible for current readers. He wanted "to gain access to Rambam [Maimonides] by starting with Cohen: Cohen is to open for us the access to Rambam." As he repeated: "Cohen is to lead us to the understanding of Rambam."³⁰ But what was the obstacle to the understanding of Rambam? In Strauss's words: "*How is it that our understanding of Rambam is in need of guidance?* Because *initially* he is *not* accessible to us. He is not accessible to us because we live in a *totally different world*: in the world of 'modern culture,' as Cohen

likes to say.³¹ Strauss's task was therefore to lead from a cultural understanding to "an original understanding of Rambam."³² The real obstacle, after all, was "our becoming enlightened," and Cohen the enlightener provided the means to grasp the principles of the Enlightenment and uproot them. As Strauss hastened to add, he would thereby "have to criticize Cohen. That is why the discussion will be more about Cohen than about Rambam, although for us it is first and last a matter of understanding Rambam."³³

The remark makes intelligible a crucial trait of many of Strauss's early writings: the glaring disproportion between the copious methodological introductions with their detailed analyses of sometimes rather innocuous *contemporary* writings, and the brief sketches – often dispersed over the texts – of the topic that really mattered. Returning to the ancients was all about gaining a proper viewpoint, and this viewpoint needed to be won in an explicit and transparent turn away from the presuppositions of the moderns. This methodological preoccupation also prevailed in *Philosophy and Law*, but the argument was built differently there.

This is not the place for a deeper analysis of *Philosophy and Law*, a highly complex study with a peculiar form or dramatic character. This form is highly relevant with regard to the methodology of returning. In other words, we must come to a better understanding of how the book works as a book. There has been some debate on whether the heterogeneous text, with its introduction and three chapters, is actually a book or merely a collection of essays. In fact, however, despite the complicated genesis, with various chapters having been written over the course of several years and being compiled literally at the last minute in early 1935, it has a very clear plan. It is an early example of what Strauss later called the "argument and action" of a philosophical book, which means that the argument is contained to some extent in the action.³⁴ This interplay between propositional content and dramatic form precedes and partly explains Strauss's later discovery of esoteric writing, but in itself there is nothing esoteric about it. *Philosophy and Law*, in particular, has often been misunderstood as an early indication of esotericism, but the inner workings of the book clearly show otherwise.³⁵ The following remarks pertain only to the beginnings of the introduction and the first chapter, which has the function of a second, methodological introduction. We may then refer to the introduction proper as the thematic introduction that situates medieval rationalism in the contemporary quarrel between orthodoxy and the Enlightenment.

The first two paragraphs of the introduction follow a unique argument and action of their own. Strauss opposed two types of rationalism to exemplify his thesis that it is actually possible to return to the position of Maimonides. He confronted modern rationalism with medieval rationalism by enacting the argument between both as a contest among equals: He juxtaposed two rationalisms and asked "which of the two opposed rationalisms is the true rationalism." The surprising answer is that modern rationalism is a "sham rationalism"³⁶ leading to the self-destruction of reason, whereas Maimonidean rationalism is the "natural model," the "standard" of rationalism.

One can hardly overemphasize the exceptional character of this starting point, in which a five-year long process of "reorientation" came to a simple and elegant formulation. Citing "the freedom of the question," Strauss demonstrated the extent to which he had moved away from the common understanding of things past.³⁷ According to the assumption of "historicism" in the broadest or most basic sense, medieval rationalism was superseded or "overcome" by the early modern rationalism of Descartes and Hobbes, and this rationalism was in turn overcome by another rationalism etc. For this historical understanding Maimonidean rationalism could not possibly be true for the mere fact that it was superseded by another doctrine. Furthermore, Maimonidean thought was bound to the outdated Aristotelian cosmology and the allegorical method of interpretation.³⁸ By 1935 Strauss had relegated these and other objections to modern prejudices. He simply compared and confronted the two rationalisms with each other as if they were coeval or simultaneous, and, even more importantly, as if medieval rationalism could be as true as modern rationalism.

The further course of the introduction moved to the modern era. Strauss staged an appeals court in which the Enlightenment case against orthodoxy is being retried, and he insinuated that some Nietzschean "atheism from probity" would serve as the "the heir and judge of the belief in revelation."³⁹ That discussion has sparked sharp controversy, and this is due to the fact that Strauss's own position remains wholly ambiguous. Scholars have particularly stumbled upon the question of whether the voice in the text is his own at this point or rather mimics the voice of Nietzsche, the quintessential figure standing at the peak of modernity. Judging from the scholarly dispute over the closing pages of the introduction, the riddle cannot be solved by way of an unequivocal argument. At least this seems so if one does not bother too much with the thesis on Maimonides, as many have done. But the riddle – and the demonstration that the riddle cannot be solved on the basis of the modern premises – was constructed to motivate the return to Maimonides in the first place. Strauss acknowledged that the situation is "unsolvable," but it is so only on the basis of "the modern premises." As he wrote: "This situation not only appears insoluble but actually is so, as long as one clings to the modern premises."⁴⁰ That sentence is the clearest outline of where Strauss actually stood, but no one believed him because no one imagined that he might actually be serious about returning to Maimonides. At this point where Strauss has led the reader all the way into a truly intricate situation, he suggested that Enlightenment is not necessarily modern Enlightenment, and the medieval Enlightenment of Maimonides and his Islamic predecessors might be the best available option.⁴¹

The second task was to make sure that the medieval solution, the solution of Maimonides, would not again be automatically interpreted within a modern framework. This is the function of the first chapter, or the second, methodological introduction to medieval Jewish philosophy. To explain what methodology means here, there is a notion of direction in his arguments: they are designed to *lead* from the seemingly evident premises to the premises of political thinking. For this reason Strauss was immensely occupied with the starting point, the proper way

to begin. The most obvious starting point for his contemporaries, he suggested, was to understand the respective matter in terms of “culture,” but its original meaning could only be understood in “political” terms. The purpose of the methodological introduction, then, is to lead from a “cultural” understanding to a “political” understanding of medieval Jewish philosophy.

In order to follow this directional argument in the text, one must pay attention to a nearly unknown *systematic* discussion. The inconspicuous topic of that discussion is the place of a doctrine within the division of philosophy. Major philosophical insights are often described with regard to a seemingly insignificant shift in the systematic disposition of a concept or doctrine. One can follow this discussion through *Philosophy and Law* and virtually all of Strauss’s later writings on Maimonides, Farabi and others.

5. Uprooting the Philosophy of Culture

A second source for Strauss’s occupation with the division of philosophy was his early acquaintance with neo-Kantian philosophy of the Marburg School. Despite many polemical remarks on Hermann Cohen, Paul Natorp and Ernst Cassirer in his works, Strauss’s philosophical project was not only a radical departure from that tradition, but paradoxically also its continuation. His discussions of the problem of political philosophy often evoke the framework of the prior debate on the systematic place of religion within the neo-Kantian division of cultural philosophy. This debate had been inaugurated by Cohen in *Der Begriff der Religion im System der Philosophie* (1915) and the introduction to *Religion der Vernunft* (1919/1929).

The initial problem faced by Cohen around 1915 pertained to the place of religion within the systematic division of philosophy. The question in short is as follows: If philosophy remains within the confines of the triadic Kantian structure of epistemology, ethics and aesthetics, where does religion belong to? Can religion be adequately described as a part of ethics? That was Cohen’s earlier solution in the *Ethics of the Pure Will* (1904). Does it require doing away with the Kantian triadic structure and allowing for a fourth pillar of the philosophical system? Cohen tried this for a while with the addition of a “psychology.” Or does the problem of religion actually destroy the Cohenian system altogether, as suggested by Franz Rosenzweig? Rosenzweig maintained in his introductory essay to Cohen’s *Jüdische Schriften* that religion could not at all be located in the system, but that it gained “systematic omnipotence.”⁴²

The reemergence of religion and the precise way it relates to the philosophical system has been a major issue in Cohen’s late work; it became a bone of contention in the quarrels in German-Jewish philosophy of the 1920s on the canonization of Cohen’s philosophy; and one can clearly show that Strauss was well familiar with the matter. One of his lasting contributions was to transfer the systematic problem to the new context of political philosophy. Eventually he also came to discuss the problem of “the political” as posed by Carl Schmitt within the conceptual framework that was build and prepared in the

prior discussion on the place of religion within the neo-Kantian system of philosophy. Religion *and* the political became recognizable through this discussion as the paradigmatic non-cultural phenomena, which therefore did not fit into the system of philosophy that was erected within the framework of neo-Kantian philosophy of culture.

Accordingly, there are two different concerns with the systematic division of philosophy here, and both are from a very different theoretical context. The place where they come together for the first time is the first chapter of *Philosophy and Law*, a biting review of Julius Guttman’s *Philosophy of Judaism* (1933). The overall strategy at the beginning of the first chapter is to situate Guttman’s study within the framework of neo-Kantian philosophy of religion, and then to show how this framework is in conflict with the subject matter of medieval philosophy. Strauss sought to demonstrate that Guttman could not understand the original problem of religion because he was trapped in the assumptions of the philosophy of culture; but as he argued “religion cannot be rightly understood in the framework of the concept of ‘culture.’”⁴³

First, culture is to be understood as the spontaneous product of the human spirit, while religion is *given* to man. Second, culture is to be understood as a set of “domains of validity,” each constituting “partial domains of truth,” while religion makes a claim to universality. In a next step Strauss rephrased these two incompatibilities as a contradiction of two oppositional claims to universality: “The claim to universality on the part of ‘culture,’ which in its own view rests in spontaneous production, seems to be opposed by the claim to universality on the part of religion, which in its own view is not produced by man but *given* to him.” With their respective claim to be universal, culture and religion do not coexist peacefully side by side, they clash with each other and seek to submit each another to their respective semantic structure. In Guttman’s *Philosophy of Judaism* religion wins the fight against culture. As Strauss described the outcome of the quarrel, Guttman “finds himself driven to a remarkable distancing from philosophy of culture by the fact of religion as such, which thereby proves to be one crux of philosophy of culture.”⁴⁴

There is much more in this beginning. In particular, Strauss did not only describe the conflict between religion and culture but added an inconspicuous third which he named “the fact of the political,” referring to Carl Schmitt’s *The Concept of the Political* once again. With this addition the conceptual framework of culture, religion and the political was completed; and it is this framework in which Strauss described the modern situation with its insoluble conflicts. We can trace the framework through a variety of his writings, including his late master lecture “Athens and Jerusalem” (1967). The text has two chapters, both of which start with a refutation of philosophy of culture. Athens and Jerusalem could only be understood (and returned to) if they were no longer misrepresented as “two cultures.” Strauss started by characterizing the position of cultural anthropology and its problematic stance toward Western cultures; and in the second part he returned to Hermann Cohen to address the possibility of understanding Jerusalem and Athens as the two sources of modern culture.

By the 1960s Strauss had two critiques of culture; one was concerned with culture as in philosophy of culture; the other was concerned with cultures, with the discovery of the infinite plurality of cultures and the infinite plurality of ideas about right and wrong. That is the *other* problematic aspect of culturalism as we know it today, with its peculiar mixture of cultural relativism and absolutism. Such negotiations in the interplay of plurality and unity – and the textual strategies he had at hand – suggest that Strauss's “return” was not just somehow philosophically backward, there is also something entirely new and unheard-of in it.

Notes

¹ L. STRAUSS, *Gesammelte Schriften*, vol. 3, ed. H./W. Meier, Metzler, Stuttgart/Weimar 1996, p. 621.

² See most recently J. A. BERNSTEIN, *Leo Strauss on the Borders of Judaism, Philosophy, and History*, SUNY Press, Albany 2015.

³ L. STRAUSS, *Gesammelte Schriften*, vol. 3, p. 661.

⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 662.

⁵ L. STRAUSS, *Jewish Philosophy and the Crisis of Modernity: Essays and Lectures in Modern Jewish Thought*, ed. K. H. Green, SUNY Press, Albany 1997, p. 450.

⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 461.

⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 87.

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ This notion of Jewish orthodoxy was of course a fiction, because in fact there never was an orthodoxy outside of history and modernity. Strauss turned orthodox Judaism into a transhistorical principle, but in reality, orthodoxy was an invention of the 19th century that came up as a response to Jewish modernity.

¹⁰ L. STRAUSS, *Philosophy and Law: Contributions to the Understanding of Maimonides and his Predecessors*, trans. E. Adler, SUNY Press 1995, Albany, p. 52.

¹¹ L. STRAUSS, *Spinoza's Critique of Religion*, Schocken, New York 1965, p. 31.

¹² L. STRAUSS, *Conspicivism*, in M. D. Yaffe/R. S. Ruderman (eds.), *Reorientation: Leo Strauss in the 1930s*, Palgrave/Macmillan, New York 2014, pp. 217-224; *Religious Situation of the Present*, *ibid.*, pp. 225-235. Strauss planned to rework the earlier essay into a larger article that would also incorporate the theses from the lecture manuscript (cf. *Gesammelte Schriften*, vol. 3, pp. 383-84), but the plan never materialized. Possibly Strauss no longer followed the idea upon the completion of his Schmitt article.

¹³ See however Timothy W. BURNS, who conceded that the text was “explicitly directed against [...] Karl Mannheim,” but nevertheless situated Strauss's talk in the critique of Heidegger. (T. W. Burns, *Strauss on the Religious and Intellectual Situation of the Present*, in Yaffe/Ruderman, *Reorientation: Leo Strauss in the 1930s*, pp. 79-113: 80) I suggest to disentangle Strauss's criticism against Mannheim from the topic of Heideggerian historicism.

¹⁴ K. MANNHEIM, *Ideologie und Utopie*, Friedrich Cohen, Bonn 1929.

¹⁵ L. STRAUSS, *Gesammelte Schriften*, vol. 3, p. 228. In a 1932 letter to Gerhard Krüger he counted Mannheim among the “idiots” (“Spranger, Maier, Mannheim, auch Höningwald ...”); *ibid.*, p. 408; cf. p. 449.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 661.

¹⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 384.

¹⁸ See Strauss's handwritten notes in the Leo Strauss Papers, The Regenstein Library, University of Chicago, box 6 folders 3 and 9.

¹⁹ L. STRAUSS, *Persecution and the Art of Writing*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago/London 1988, p. 7.

²⁰ L. STRAUSS, *The Political Philosophy of Hobbes: Its Basis and Its Genesis*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago/London 1966, p. 144n1.

²¹ L. STRAUSS, *Persecution and the Art of Writing*, p. 7.

²² *Ibid.*, pp. 7-8.

²³ *Ibid.*, p. 25.

²⁴ L. STRAUSS, *Conspicivism*, in *Reorientation*, p. 222.

²⁵ L. STRAUSS, *Religious Situation of the Present*, in *Reorientation*, pp. 231-32.

²⁶ Cf. L. STRAUSS, *Besprechung von Julius Ebbinghaus, Über die Fortschritte der Metaphysik*, in *Gesammelte Schriften*, vol. 2, pp. 437-39: 439.

²⁷ L. STRAUSS, *Gesammelte Schriften*, vol. 3, p. 615.

²⁸ L. STRAUSS, *Notes on Carl Schmitt, The Concept of the Political*, in H. Meier, *Carl Schmitt and Leo Strauss: The Hidden Dialogue*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago/London, pp. 91-119: 119.

²⁹ L. STRAUSS, *Cohen and Maimonides*, in K. H. Green (ed.), *Leo Strauss on Maimonides: The Complete Writings*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago/London 2013, pp. 173-222: 174.

³⁰ *Ibid.*, pp. 175, 177.

³¹ *Ibid.*, p. 177.

³² *Ibid.*, p. 178.

³³ *Ibid.*, p. 175 (trans. altered).

³⁴ L. STRAUSS, *The Argument and the Action of Plato's Laws*, Chicago 1975.

³⁵ Cf. P. VON WUSSOW, *Leo Strauss and Julius Guttman: Some Remarks on the Understanding of Philosophy and Law*, in *Idealistic Studies*, 44 (2015) 2-3, pp. 297-312.

³⁶ L. STRAUSS, *Philosophy and Law*, p. 22 (trans. altered).

³⁷ *Ibid.*

³⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 39.

³⁹ *Ibid.*, pp. 38-39.

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 38.

⁴¹ Chapters two and three of *Philosophy and Law* are devoted to the elaboration of this option in terms of medieval philosophy. The limits of the present article forbid to do more than hint at a forthcoming larger interpretation of these chapters.

⁴² F. ROSENZWEIG, *Einleitung*, in: H. Cohen, *Jüdische Schriften*, vol. 1, Schwetschke, Berlin 1924, pp. xiii-lxiv: xlvi.

⁴³ L. STRAUSS, *Philosophy and Law*, p. 42.

⁴⁴ *Ibid.*